
Dakwah Without Fees: Spiritual Transformation of the Cool Preachers Community through the Philosophy of 'Ikhlas Ruhnya Dakwah' in South Sulawesi

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Abstract:

This study aims to analyze the da'wah strategy of the Pendakwah Keren Community (KPK) through the slogan "Ikhlas Ruhnya Dakwah" (Sincerity is the Spirit of Da'wah) in South Sulawesi. The focus of this study is on how this community interprets and implements the value of sincerity as the spirit of da'wah in its activities, and how this strategy shapes a positive image in the eyes of the community. This study uses a qualitative approach with a case study method. Data were obtained through in-depth interviews, participatory observation, and documentation of KPK activities in various regions in South Sulawesi. The results show that the KPK implements six main strategic steps in carrying out the slogan "Ikhlas Ruhnya Dakwah": internalization of the value of sincerity through spiritual regeneration, implementation of social da'wah without expecting anything in return, program selection based on the value of sincerity, leadership that exemplifies sincerity, evaluation based on intention rather than outward achievements, and maintenance of sincerity through dhikr and muhasabah. The urgency of developing the KPK's da'wah strategy is driven by socio-cultural changes in society, internal community challenges, the need to strengthen the implementation of the slogan's values, expansion into marginalized areas, and the professionalization of da'wah without losing its spiritual essence. The strengths of the KPK's strategy include an emphasis on spiritual values that distinguish it from commercial da'wah, a non-competitive and inclusive approach, spirituality-based cadre development, and flexibility in da'wah methods. Its weaknesses include the absence of objective measures to assess sincerity, high dependence on individual motivation, and a weak organizational management system, all of which lead to program inconsistency. The slogan "Ikhlas Ruhnya Dakwah" (Sincerity in Preaching) serves as the philosophical foundation guiding all of the KPK's preaching activities, ensuring they remain focused on the ultimate goal of pleasing Allah, without getting caught up in materialism or popularity. This study is expected to contribute to contemporary preaching strategies and serve as a reference for other preaching communities in developing strategies that are relevant, creative, and rooted in the value of sincerity.

Keywords: Da'wah, Cool Da'wah Community, Sincerity in the Spirit of Da'wah.

INTRODUCTION

Dakwah, as an activity to spread Islamic values, faces complex challenges in the contemporary era, marked by socio-cultural transformations, the digital revolution, and shifts in the information consumption patterns of the millennial generation. This phenomenon requires a reconfiguration of dakwah methodologies that can maintain spiritual authenticity while responding to the dynamics of the times. (Aziza, 2009). The Qur'an has provided fundamental guidelines for da'wah, as stated by Allah SWT in Surah An-Nahl verse 125: "Invite (people) to the way of your Lord with wisdom and good instruction, and argue with them in a way that is best." This verse indicates that da'wah requires a wise approach, good material, and an appropriate delivery method according to the context of the audience.

From the perspective of da'wah communication theory, Jalaluddin Rakhmat (Rakhmat, 2004) Emphasizes that the effectiveness of da'wah is not only determined by the quality of the message but also by the communication strategy used by the dai in delivering the message to the mad'u. This aligns with Deci and Ryan's self-determination theory, which shows that intrinsic motivation, such as sincerity in preaching, leads to greater consistency and resilience than extrinsic motivation. In the context of Islamic da'wah, this principle is reflected in the Prophet's hadith "*innamal a'malu bin niyyat*," which affirms the supremacy of intention as a determinant of the quality of deeds. Al-Ghazali in *Ihya Ulumuddin* further explains that sincerity is the heart of righteous deeds, giving birth to perseverance and courage to convey the truth, even if it is unpopular.

Previous research on community da'wah strategies has been conducted with various focuses. Juangsah et al. (Juansyah et al., 2022) Examined the professionalism of the Komunitas Pendakwah Keren (KPK) in improving the religious understanding of the people of Makassar, finding that the KPK's professionalism was reflected in its consistent schedule and high commitment to the program. Lulu et al. (Lulu Khumairo et al., 2023) Analyzed the digital da'wah strategies of the Samarinda Community Preachers through three approaches: *manhaj al-'athifi* (emotional), *manhaj al-aqli* (rational), and *manhaj al-hissi* (sensorial), which showed the adaptability of the Community Preachers to digital media. Gunawan (Gunawan, 2024) Identified the main programs of the KPK Parepare, such as Subuh Adventure and Majelis Dzikir Al-Awwabien, with the strategies of *bil-hikmah*, *al-mauidzah al-hasanah*, and *al-mujadalah*. Meanwhile, (Abdurrahman, 2020) In his study on Pemuda Hijrah Bandung, he confirms the importance of symbols and slogans in building the image of contemporary community da'wah.

However, these studies still have limitations in analyzing how spiritual values, especially sincerity, are operationalized into concrete and sustainable da'wah strategies. Previous studies have focused more on methodological and programmatic aspects without delving deeply into the philosophy underlying community da'wah strategies.

The Pendakwah Keren (KPK) community, founded by KH. Raden Ahmad Affandi, in 2017, represents an interesting phenomenon in the development of contemporary da'wah in Indonesia. KPK carries the slogan "Ikhlās Ruhnya Dakwah" (Sincerity is the Spirit of Da'wah) as its philosophical

foundation, which distinguishes it from other da'wah communities. In South Sulawesi, the KPK has expanded into 14 zones spread across various districts/cities, demonstrating the adaptability and sustainability of a values-based da'wah model in the Bugis-Makassar sociocultural context. The people of South Sulawesi, with their cultural philosophy of "siri' na pacce" (pride and empathy), resonate with the value of sincerity () promoted by the KPK, providing an ideal context for analyzing the implementation of spiritual value-based da'wah strategies.

This study aims to analyze the da'wah strategy of the South Sulawesi Cool Preachers Community through the implementation of the slogan "Ikhlas Ruhnya Dakwah" (Sincerity is the Spirit of Da'wah), focusing on three main aspects. First, to identify and describe the strategic steps taken by the KPK in implementing the slogan as an operational guide for da'wah. Second, to analyze the urgency of developing the KPK's da'wah strategy in the context of contemporary da'wah challenges and the social dynamics of modern society. Third, to evaluate the strengths and weaknesses of implementing a da'wah strategy based on the value of sincerity and its implications for the sustainability of the community's da'wah movement. This research is expected to contribute to the study of contemporary da'wah strategies and serve as a reference for other da'wah communities in developing relevant, creative strategies that remain rooted in Islamic spiritual values.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study uses a qualitative approach with a case study method to analyze the implementation of the preaching strategy of the Cool Preachers Community (KPK) through the slogan "Ikhlas Ruhnya Dakwah" (Sincere Preaching) in South Sulawesi. The qualitative approach was chosen to gain an in-depth understanding of the meaning, process, and dynamics of applying the value of sincerity in the community's da'wah activities, which cannot be measured quantitatively (Creswell & Poth, 2018). The case study method allows researchers to explore contemporary phenomena in the context of real life, maintaining clear boundaries between the phenomenon and its context, even when these boundaries are not easily determined. Yin & Campbell, 2018).

The research was conducted in 14 KPK zones in South Sulawesi, including Makassar, Gowa, Takalar, Bantaeng, Bulukumba, Sinjai, Bone, Wajo, Sidrap, Pinrang, Pare-Pare, Barru, Pangkep, and Maros. These locations were chosen because the fourteen zones represent the implementation of the KPK's da'wah strategy in South Sulawesi, with variations in the demographic and socio-cultural characteristics of the communities. The research subjects were selected using purposive sampling with the criteria of having in-depth knowledge of the KPK's da'wah strategy and active involvement in the implementation of the slogan "Ikhlas Ruhnya Dakwah" (Patton, 2015). The purposive sampling technique was chosen because the researchers needed informants who had specific characteristics and could provide rich information in accordance with the research objectives (Djamba & Neuman, 2002).

The research informants consisted of 12 people categorized as key and supporting informants. The key informants included IPDA Muhammad Hilal, as the South Sulawesi KPK Regional Coordinator, and KH. Raden Ahmad Affandi, as the Founder of KPK Indonesia, had full authority to explain the

concept and implementation of community da'wah strategies. Supporting informants included eight regional coordinators, KPK preachers, and administrators from various zones, selected based on their experience and active involvement in community da'wah activities. In addition, the study also involved triangulation of informants in the form of community leaders and congregations who participated in the KPK's (Spradley, 2016). to obtain an external perspective on the effectiveness of the da'wah strategy implemented.

Research data was collected through three main techniques, namely in-depth interviews, participatory observation, and documentation. In-depth interviews were conducted using a semi-structured approach to explore informants' understanding of the implementation of the slogan "Ikhlas Ruhnya Dakwah" in daily da'wah practices, the challenges faced, and the strategies applied in developing the community. (Kvale & Brinkmann, 2015). Participatory observation was conducted at various KPK activities, including Subuh Adventure, Dakwah Camp, Dzikir Al-Awwabin, and regular studies in various zones, focusing on interaction patterns, dakwah methods, and the manifestation of sincerity in community activities (Spradley, 2016). Documentation included collecting photos of activities, videos of lectures, KPK social media posts, and internal training materials relevant to the implementation of da'wah strategies based on sincerity (Bowen, 2009).

Data analysis uses Miles and Huberman's interactive model, which consists of three main components: data reduction, data display, and data verification (Miles et al., 2014). Data reduction is carried out through a process of sorting and focusing on data relevant to the KPK's da'wah strategy. Data is presented in narrative text and matrices to facilitate the identification of patterns and relationships between concepts. Data verification was conducted, resulting in consistent findings supported by valid data from various sources.

Data validity was ensured through source triangulation and technique triangulation to ensure the credibility of the research findings (Lincoln, 1990). Source triangulation was carried out by comparing information obtained from various categories of informants to identify consistency and differences in perspectives on the implementation of the KPK's da'wah strategy. Technique triangulation was carried out by confirming the interview data with observation and documentation findings to obtain a comprehensive picture of the phenomenon being studied (Denzin & Lincoln, 2018). In addition, member checking was conducted to ensure the accuracy of the researcher's interpretation of the informants' perspectives and experiences in implementing the slogan "Ikhlas Ruhnya Dakwah" as a community da'wah strategy (Creswell, 2017).

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The Pendakwah Keren Community (KPK) was born from a long journey experienced by KH—Raden Ahmad Affandi as its founder. Before establishing KPK, he had tried various breakthroughs in da'wah methodology through several organizations such as Ahlishshuffah Center, Medang Cinta, and Komunitas Cinta Dakwah. Based on in-depth interviews, KH. Raden was concerned about the existing patterns of preaching, where many preachers or ustadz preferred to preach in urban areas, leaving the suburban communities. This condition created a gap in access for marginalized communities to well-known ustadz due to limited information, accommodation, and high costs. This phenomenon has led many ustadz to refrain from engaging in da'wah among the lower strata of society and instead choose to become 'da'wah artists' with busy schedules and high honoraria.

Research findings show that KH. Raden sought to make a breakthrough in preaching by reaching out to people in villages and rural areas. He invited preachers to create study programs, knowledge assemblies, and preaching networks in various places, regardless of the costs, distance, or conditions of the preaching terrain. The philosophy underlying this movement is the understanding that preachers are servants of Allah, conveyors of the Prophet's message, and bearers of religious trust, so it is only natural that they should struggle and sacrifice in spreading the religion. This approach is in line with Burns' (1979) The concept of transformative leadership emphasizes a paradigm shift for the greater good.

KPK was founded in Samarinda, East Kalimantan, on April 10, 2017, with a vision to build the morality and spirituality of society based on Islamic values that are rahmatan lil alamiin (a blessing for all creation) and uphold the values of a diverse but unified nation. The mission of this community covers three main aspects: first, making the KPK a forum for preachers to carry out da'wah activities in spreading the benefits of knowledge and building a network of people who follow Ahlus Sunnah Wal Jamaah; second, understanding the economic potential of the Muslim community and providing solutions to social problems; third, establishing majelis taklim (Islamic study groups) and Islamic studies to develop a spirituality-based civilization within the framework of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia and the 1945 Constitution.

The motto "Ikhlash Ruhnya Dakwah" (Sincerity in Preaching), which is based on the Qur'an, Hadith, and Ijma' Ulama, is the core value that distinguishes the KPK from other preaching communities. Observations show that the KPK aims to develop a da'wah methodology based on the principles of togetherness, programs that are in line with the times, and dais who excel in material, delivery, and attractive appearance. In South Sulawesi, the KPK has expanded into 14 zones spread across various regencies and cities, including Makassar, Gowa, Takalar, Bantaeng, Bulukumba, Sinjai, Bone, Wajo, Sidrap, Pinrang, Pare-Pare, Barru, Pangkep, and Maros.

According to IPDA Muhammad Hilal, the Regional Coordinator of the KPK in South Sulawesi, preachers must dedicate themselves sincerely and wholeheartedly, with a long-term vision and mission to build the welfare of the people. The main characteristic of this community is the application of the principle of preaching without fees, as stated in an interview: "The KPK is flexible;

it is not allowed to charge fees, but if given, it is okay to accept. Because the motto is that sincerity is the spirit of preaching. If anyone charges fees, they will be immediately dismissed." This principle reflects a commitment to the value of sincerity that is not only symbolic but also implemented in firm and consistent operational policies (Weber, 1964).

A. Strategic Steps in Implementing the Slogan "Sincerity in the Spirit of Da'wah "

The implementation of the slogan "Sincerity in the Spirit of Da'wah " as a KPK da'wah strategy is carried out through six integrated strategic steps. First, internalizing the value of sincerity in cadre development makes the process the starting point for instilling this value. Each new member is guided to understand that dakwah is a form of worship that is only valuable if done for Allah, not for personal interests, popularity, or material gain. This process is carried out through spiritual training such as halaqah, tadabbur, mentoring, and Islamic character building with an emphasis on the intentions and motivations of dakwah and the stories of the struggles of the Prophets and scholars in maintaining sincerity. The theological basis for this approach refers to the hadith of the Prophet,

"إِنَّمَا الْأَعْمَالُ بِالنِّيَّاتِ", which emphasizes that the value of deeds is determined by intentions (Al-Bukhari & Muslim).

The interview with IPDA Muhammad Hilal confirmed that "one of the strategic steps taken by the Pendakwah Keren Community in instilling the value of sincerity is through regeneration." This finding is in line with Bandura's (1977) social learning theory, which emphasizes the importance of modeling and observational learning in character building. The KPK uses a transformative learning approach that not only transfers knowledge but also changes the paradigm and spiritual orientation of its preaching cadres.

Second, selfless preaching through social movements that demonstrate a commitment to sincerity through social actions that are not commercialized and do not expect rewards. The main programs include the "Subuh Berkah" social preaching movement, natural disaster relief, the collection of donations from internal members without relying on large sponsors, and Subuh Adventure, which extends from urban areas to remote villages. All activities are carried out voluntarily without expecting massive publicity. Musawwir, Regional Secretary of the KPK Takalar Zone, emphasized that "with social da'wah carried out by the KPK as a strategic step to make da'wah more memorable in the community, seeing that there are still many people who need help due to economic factors."

Third, program selection is based on sincerity, where the KPK does not merely pursue popularity or the number of followers but chooses sustainable activities, even if they are not viral on social media. Priority programs include fardiyah da'wah (individual approach) in marginalized environments, distribution of the Qur'an in remote areas, and the formation of small discussion groups for spiritual guidance. Muhammad Yusuf Jufri, Regional Secretary of the KPK Gowa Zone, explained that "preaching is not only done on the pulpit but can also be done through discussion and openness with the community as a strategic step of the Cool Preachers Community." This approach

reflects the application of *dakwah bil hikmah*, which emphasizes wisdom in choosing methods and targets for preaching (Aziza, 2009).

Fourth, leadership that inspires sincerity by selecting leaders based on integrity and character, not merely managerial skills. Leaders are expected to set a direct example in charitable deeds, not take advantage of their organizational positions, and focus more on serving members and the community. Leadership in the KPK is understood not as a tool of power, but as a trust that must be accounted for in the hereafter. Mubayyinul Haq, KPK Zone Gowa Coordinator, emphasized that "a leader must be an example or role model for its members as a manifestation of successful *da'wah*." This concept is in line with the servant leadership theory developed by Greenleaf (2002), where a true leader serves their followers.

Fifth, evaluation is based on intention rather than outward achievements. The KPK places more emphasis on whether activities are carried out with pure intentions, whether members experience spiritual growth, and whether the program leaves a positive impact, even if small. Although statistics and achievement reports are still taken into account, they are not the primary measure of success. Jusriadi Gama, a member of the KPK Gowa Zone, stated that "running a program requires evaluation as a means to improve what needs to be improved and maintain what needs to be maintained."

Sixth, maintaining sincerity through *zikr* and *muhasabah* to preserve the spirit of sincerity within members through collective *zikr*, night prayers, recitation of the Quran to evaluate intentions and deeds, and *taushiyah* forums to remind each other to maintain their intentions. Ferry Vibriyansyah, General Treasurer of the KPK South Sulawesi, explained that "to maintain sincerity, we must always remind each other because sometimes a preacher forgets, as this is human nature." This approach reflects the application of the concept of *ta'awun* (mutual assistance) in maintaining the purity of intentions, as emphasized in the Quran (QS. (Al-Maidah: 2)).

B. The Urgency of Developing a Da'wah Strategy for the KPK

The development of a KPK *da'wah* strategy is urgently needed due to five main factors identified in the study. First, social and cultural changes in society, triggered by globalization, technology, and the flow of information, have influenced the younger generation's view of religion. The KPK needs to adjust its *da'wah* approach to remain relevant, as traditional *da'wah* that is rigid or too formal is often no longer accepted by the digital generation. The younger generation responds better to communication that is fast, visual, and entertaining yet still substantial, so the value of sincerity must be packaged creatively and touchingly. This finding is supported by a statement from Faried Milenial, Regional Secretary of the KPK in South Sulawesi: "Dakwah in the millennial era requires a different approach, because the younger generation today has unique characteristics; they are more open to information and more active in using social media." This analysis aligns with Prensky's (2001), The theory of digital natives explains the characteristics of a generation raised in the digital technology era.

Second, the KPK faces internal challenges within the community, requiring strategic improvements due to varying levels of understanding among cadres, program sustainability issues,

and the absence of a standardized organizational management system. Without a continuously developed strategy, the KPK risks losing its direction and core strength as a community of da'wah cadres. Muhammad Yusuf Jufri, Regional Secretary of the KPK Gowa Zone, acknowledged that "The Pendakwah Keren Community must reform itself from the programs that have been implemented because currently there are many institutions and da'wah communities that pose their own challenges." These challenges require the application of organizational development theory, which emphasizes continuous adaptation to internal and external environmental changes (Cummings, 2014).

Third, strengthening the value of the slogan "Ikhlas Ruhnya Dakwah" (Sincerity is the Spirit of Da'wah) as the spiritual identity of the KPK, which in practice is often threatened by social media pressure, competition for existence, and achievement orientation. Strategic development is crucial to ensure that programs remain focused on the intention of lillah, activities do not lose their spiritual essence and become empty routines, and da'wah evaluations cover aspects of intention and sincerity, not just the quantity of participants. KH. Raden Ahmad Affandi, Founder of KPK Indonesia, reflected: "The slogan Ikhlas Ruhnya Dakwah is crucial to continue to be emphasized in every community activity. Without sincerity, da'wah can become an empty routine, merely a formality devoid of spiritual meaning." This statement confirms Imam Al-Ghazali's view in *Ihya Ulumuddin* that maintaining sincerity is more difficult than performing the act itself.

Fourth, reaching new areas and target groups where the KPK needs a da'wah expansion strategy, so as not to focus only on urban environments and communities that are already religious. A different approach is needed for the general public, marginalized communities, and even non-Muslims through methods such as da'wah *bil hal* (da'wah through action), art, culture, and social media. Inclusive da'wah with a cultural strategy will make the KPK a truly down-to-earth da'wah movement. Sultan Abidin, a member of the Takalar Zone KPK, articulated this vision: "Reaching new areas and targets is a tangible form of the spirit of da'wah that continues to move forward. The KPK should not only focus on cities or places that are frequently visited. Remote areas, marginalized communities, and even informal groups such as online motorcycle taxi drivers or street children also need to be touched by da'wah."

Fifth, professionalizing da'wah without losing its spirit, where professional da'wah does not mean losing spiritual values. With a well-planned strategy, the KPK can improve the quality of its cadres and programs, making da'wah activities more structured and widespread, and strengthening public trust. Zein Asfar Affandy, Secretary General of the Indonesian KPK, explains: "The professionalization of da'wah is critical in this day and age. The KPK has already begun moving in that direction with more structured program management, well-organized da'wah activity scheduling, and effective use of media. However, what I appreciate is that they continue to emphasize the values of sincerity and the spiritual spirit of da'wah." This approach is in line with al-Qaradawi's concept of a dai who is not only required to be sincere, but also to have strategies, competencies, and the ability to convey messages effectively (Qaradhawi, 2022).

C. Strengths and Weaknesses of the KPK's Da'wah Strategy

An in-depth analysis of the KPK's da'wah strategy reveals a dialectic between structural strengths and potential weaknesses in the implementation of the slogan "Ikhlas Ruhnya Dakwah" (Sincerity is the Spirit of Da'wah). Four main strengths have been identified, reflecting the competitive advantages of this community in the contemporary da'wah landscape.

The first strength is the emphasis on spiritual values as the main orientation, which makes sincerity the spirit of da'wah and a distinguishing value that prevents activities from being commercialized or merely for image-building. This advantage is based on the hadith of the Prophet narrated by An-Nasa'i: "إِنَّ اللَّهَ لَا يَنْظُرُ إِلَى صُورِكُمْ وَ أَمْوَالِكُمْ وَ لَكِن يَنْظُرُ إِلَى قُلُوبِكُمْ وَ أَعْمَالِكُمْ" (Verily, Allah does not look at your appearance and wealth, but He looks at your hearts and deeds). KH. Raden Affandi, Founder of KPK Indonesia, explained: "Dakwah is not just an activity of delivering material or lectures, but more than that, dakwah is the work of the heart. Therefore, spirituality is the main foundation. If spirituality is weak, da'wah becomes dry and does not touch people's hearts." Mubayyinul Haq, Regional Coordinator of KPK Zone Gowa, confirmed that "the emphasis on spirituality makes us realize that the success of da'wah is not measured by the number of followers or the virality of the content, but by how sincere and lillah the activities are."

The second strength is a non-competitive and inclusive approach to da'wah, where the KPK avoids competing for popularity on social media and instead chooses a down-to-earth, personal approach. This is in line with the concept of dakwah bil hikmah and mauidzah hasanah as stated by Allah in QS—an-Nahl verse 125. Zainuddin, a dai from the KPK Gowa Zone, explained: "One of the things that distinguishes the KPK from many other communities is its non-competitive approach to dakwah. We do not see dakwah as a competition to see who is the most popular or has the most followers. The focus is on usefulness, so we do not compete but rather strengthen each other." Jusriadi Gama added: "The principle of the KPK is to embrace, not to judge. Competitive da'wah will only give rise to ego and jealousy among da'wah workers."

The third strength is spirituality-based cadre development, whereby KPK cadres are trained through internal recitation and Al-Awwabin zikr to develop spiritual resilience. This strategy creates preachers who are not easily swayed by worldly temptations. KH. Raden Ahmad Affandi explained: "The cadre development process at the KPK is not only about strengthening the material aspects of preaching, but also places great emphasis on shaping the heart and soul. One form of this is the habit of reciting prayers together, which serves as spiritual 'charging' so that each cadre is truly mentally and spiritually prepared when preaching." This approach is in line with the theory of spiritual intelligence developed by Zohar and Marshall (2001), which emphasizes the importance of spiritual intelligence in facing life's challenges.

The fourth strength is the flexibility of methods, whereby the KPK combines various media for preaching, ranging from face-to-face meetings to social media and social activities. This demonstrates the ability to adapt to the current context without abandoning the main principles. The

informants explained that the KPK is not fixated on a particular form or style of preaching, but is contextual in nature, adapting to the characteristics of the audience, location, and developments of the times. This approach stems from the awareness that preaching methods are a vehicle, not an end in themselves. Therefore, innovation and creativity are highly encouraged, as long as the substance of the message remains in line with Islamic teachings.

However, the KPK's strategy has three fundamental weaknesses that require serious attention. The first weakness is the absence of an objective measure of sincerity. The value of sincerity is understood as a very personal inner matter between the preacher and Allah SWT, so it cannot be used as an external benchmark in assessing the quality of preaching. Prof. Dr. Nurhidayat Muh Said, Professor at UIN Alauddin Makassar, emphasized: "Sincerity is not something that can be measured from the outside. There are no definite parameters for assessing whether a dai is truly sincere or not, because sincerity is very personal." This condition creates an evaluation paradox where the effectiveness of the strategy becomes subjective and difficult to verify empirically. On the positive side, it prevents the community from developing a competitive culture in da'wah activities.

The second weakness is the high dependence on individual motivation, where the KPK's da'wah system is not based on a rigid hierarchical and command structure, but rather on the spiritual awareness and personal will of the cadres. Informants said that there is no formal assessment system or targets in the implementation of da'wah programs, so effectiveness is highly dependent on the internal drive of each dai. Although this approach is in line with Ryan and Deci's (2000) The theory of self-determination, which emphasizes intrinsic motivation, suggests that not all cadres have the same level of motivation and spiritual maturity in practice, potentially leading to program inconsistencies.

The third weakness is weak organizational management, as the KPK's strategy lacks support from modern managerial systems such as standard operating procedures, data-based evaluation, or adequate documentation of activities. Muhammad Yusuf Jufri acknowledged: "There is a high spirit of togetherness, but weak management. For example, in reporting, activity evaluation, or cadre regeneration, it is not yet systematic. Because the KPK grew out of a community, it is not yet a well-organized institution." This condition weakens the continuity and sustainability of the program, potentially hindering the achievement of a broader and more professional da'wah mission in the long term. According to Umar (2014), sustainable da'wah requires an organizational system that is structured, planned, and capable of systematically preparing for the regeneration of dai.

CONCLUSION

Research on the strategies of the Komunitas Pendakwah Keren (KPK) through the slogan "Ikhlās Ruhnya Dakwah" in South Sulawesi reveals a contemporary da'wah model that successfully integrates traditional spiritual values with a modern methodological approach. The findings show that the KPK has developed a da'wah paradigm that is responsive to the challenges of the times without sacrificing the authenticity of the religious message.

First, the KPK represents the evolution of a preaching movement born out of criticism of the elitism and commercialization of conventional preaching and founded by KH. In 2017, Raden Ahmad Affandi successfully established a preaching network for this community, covering 14 zones in South Sulawesi, based on the fundamental principle of rejecting a preaching fee system. The philosophy of "Ikhlās Ruhnya Dakwah" (Sincerity in Preaching) has proven to be more than just a slogan; it is an epistemological construct that underlies all community activities and distinguishes it from other preaching movements.

Second, the implementation of the KPK's da'wah strategy is carried out through six integrated dimensions: internalization of the value of sincerity in transformative cadre development, selfless social da'wah, value-based program selection, leadership that inspires sincerity, evaluation based on spiritual intent and impact, and maintenance of sincerity through collective dhikr and muhasabah. This approach reflects a synthesis of transformative learning theory, servant leadership, and spiritual intelligence in the context of contemporary Islamic da'wah.

Third, the urgency of developing the KPK's da'wah strategy is driven by five imperatives: socio-cultural changes in the digital society, internal challenges within the community, strengthening spiritual identity, expansion into marginalized areas and targets, and professionalization without losing the spirit of da'wah. These findings confirm the theories of digital natives and organizational development, which emphasize the importance of continuously adapting to the dynamics of both internal and external environments.

Fourth, SWOT analysis reveals the dialectic between the strengths and weaknesses of the KPK's strategy. The main strengths include an emphasis on spiritual values as a distinctive advantage, a non-competitive and inclusive approach, spirituality-based cadre development, and flexibility in da'wah methodology. However, this strategy faces three fundamental weaknesses: the lack of objective measurability of sincerity, high dependence on individual motivation, and a weak organizational management system.

Fifth, theoretically, this research contributes to the development of transformative da'wah studies that integrate spiritual dimensions with contemporary methodologies. The KPK's da'wah model offers an alternative paradigm that proves the possibility of maintaining spiritual authenticity while responding to the contextual demands of the times. The success in building a committed community of dai without a material incentive system confirms the theory of intrinsic motivation in religious behavior.

Sixth, practically, the research findings show that the long-term sustainability of the sincerity-based dakwah model requires resolution of the tension between spiritual idealism and organizational pragmatism. The KPK's future development strategy needs to integrate a systematic management approach without compromising the spiritual foundation, which is the community's comparative advantage.

This study proves that contemporary da'wah can maintain sacred values while adopting innovative approaches. However, the sustainability of this model depends on overcoming the paradox between

the unmeasurability of sincerity and the demand for organizational effectiveness. The main contribution of this research is the empirical demonstration that sincerity can function as a measurable da'wah strategy through social and spiritual impacts, even though it cannot be quantified conventionally.

The KPK da'wah model serves as an essential reference for developing da'wah movements that respond to contemporary social dynamics while maintaining spiritual integrity. It has relevant implications for the study of persuasive communication, value-based organizational management, and the sociology of religion in the context of modern Indonesia.

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